

Access to social science and official statistics data

Irena Vipavc Brvar

EF, 25.10.2017

Social Science Data Archives, University of Ljubljana

- 1997
- **national research infrastructure for social sciences**
- depositors from all 4 universities, private research centres, Statistical Office of Slovenia
- 600 social science surveys
- cca. 700 users yearly (90 % education, 10 % scientific/research purpose)
- ADP is the only research data repository in Slovenia
- Member of [CESSDA ERIC](#)
- International projects (DwB, Foster, SEEDS, SaW, SERISS ...)

Our mission is »to ensure and promote sustainable services of ingest, storage and access to quality research data from the field of Slovenian social sciences and broader, with potential for secondary analysis«

1. ADP evaluates the importance of research data for science and their long-term usability.
2. Adopts an acknowledged digital curation approach.
3. Provides access to data and enables searching and browsing through standard data descriptions for the purposes of discovery.
4. Offers support with data management planning and preparation of data for open access.

Research data

„...constitute primary sources that underpin scientific research and enable derivation of theoretical or applied findings.“

(Preparing research data for open access, Guide for data producers, 2015, p.1)

PUBLICATIONS AND DATA

Source: Research data alliance meeting 2014

Open access – open data – open science

„The basic principle of open access is the immediate availability of publicly funded research results on the World Wide Web without any subscription or copyright restrictions.“

(<http://www.openaccess.si/definicije-in-deklaracije/>)

DATA SHARING

RECOVERY OF DATA

ADP curates data for reuse:

ensures that data is preserved against technological obsolescence and physical destruction.

LOSS OF DATA

ADP:

confirms and prepares data and relevant documentation with the intention of long-term digital preservation and secondary use.

ADP provides users with **easy access to data in many formats.**

INFORMATION TYPES

Study topics in ADP

Study Topics

CESSDA Topic Classification

CERIF Topic Classification

- DEMOGRAPHY, POPULATION, VITAL STATISTICS AND CENSUSES
- ECONOMICS
- EDUCATION
- HEALTH
- HOUSING AND LAND USE PLANNING
- INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
- LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT
- LAW, CRIME AND LEGAL SYSTEMS
- NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- Not categorized
- OTHER
- POLITICS
- PSYCHOLOGY
- SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
- SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS
- SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND SYSTEMS
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE
- TRADE, INDUSTRY AND MARKETS
- TRANSPORT, TRAVEL AND MOBILITY

SOCIETY AND CULTURE

- SOCIETY AND CULTURE, 153 researches
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE - community, urban and rural life, 23 researches
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE - cultural and national identity, 10 researches
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE - leisure, tourism and sport, 11 researches
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE - religion and values, 10 researches
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE - social behaviour and attitudes, 81 researches
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE - social conditions and indicators, 34 researches
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE - time use, 7 researches

How can I use available contents?

- To compare the content / results of my survey with the results of comparable surveys in more general/other populations.
- To compare the content/results of my survey with past surveys.
- To use secondary resources available to me (SAVING TIME and MONEY)
 - Comparison between different time points
 - Among various research
 - Use of different sources / official statistics / cartograms
 - International comparison
- I can use tested questionnaires for my research.
- I can use attached materials for the theoretical basis of my work.

Using microdata, questionnaire and publications

What do we need for understanding and proper interpretation

Metadata can be defined as "all the information needed to inform and process statistical structures".

(Grossmann v Vipavc in Klep, 2003).

The specification used in the field of social sciences and humanities is the DDI.

What are metadata in ADP?

- ✓ Author
- ✓ Producer
- ✓ Financial support
- ✓ Series
- ✓ Study topics
- ✓ Abstract
- ✓ Collection date
- ✓ Time production
- ✓ Geographic cover
- ✓ Unit of analysis
- ✓ Population
- ✓ Collector
- ✓ Sampling
- ✓ Weighting
- ✓ Citing
- ✓ Related studies
- ✓ Questionnaires and accompanying materials

[Use data /](#) [ADP Catalogue /](#) [pbsi1209](#)

Politbarometer 09/12, Slovenia: September 2012

[Study description](#) [Data description](#) [Accompanying Materials](#) [Nesstar Browser](#)

Basic Study Information

ADP - IDNo: PBSI1209

Main author(s):

Kurdija, Slavko
Toš, Niko

[Other co-workers »](#)

Data file producer:

CJM - Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre (Ljubljana, Slovenia, 2012)

Funding agency:

Agencija za raziskovalno dejavnost Republike Slovenije = Slovenian Research Agency

Series:

- [PB/Politbarometer, Slovenija = Politbarometer, Slovenia More »](#)

How to CITE this study?

Kurdija, Slavko and Niko Toš. Politbarometer 09/12, Slovenia: September 2012 [data file]. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre [production], 2012. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov = Social Science Data Archives [distribution], 2013. ADP - IDNo: PBSI1209.

How to get data from ADP?

WEBSITE

www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si

NESSTAR

<http://nesstar2.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

The image shows two overlapping screenshots. The left screenshot is the ADP - Social Science Data Archives website, featuring a navigation bar with 'USE DATA', 'DEPOSIT STUDY', 'LEARN ABOUT', and 'DISCOVER ADP'. Below the navigation bar is a search bar and a list of studies by study ID. The right screenshot is the Nesstar WebView interface, titled 'Catalog of ADP in Nesstar', which provides information about the WebView capabilities and a warning about data analysis.

ADP - SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA ARCHIVES

Analyze data! Deposit study! Promote science!

Subscribe to eNews

USE DATA DEPOSIT STUDY LEARN ABOUT DISCOVER ADP

Use data / / ADP Catalogue

List of studies by study's ID

Study ID	Study title, topic	Access
AA	Alpe - Adria regions topic: SOCIETY AND CULTURE, SOCIETY AND CULTURE - cultural and national identity, produced by: CJM	nesstar
ABR97	Aufbruch 1997 topic: SOCIETY AND CULTURE, SOCIETY AND CULTURE - social behaviour and attitudes, SOCIETY AND CULTURE - religion and values, produced by: CJMMK	nesstar
ADPUSE16	ADP users satisfaction survey, 2016 topic: INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION, produced by: None	nesstar
ADS	Labour force survey. Series information series: ADS, topic: LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT - employment, produced by: SORS	nesstar

WebView Nesstar enables:

- viewing of studies,
- performing analyses of microdata,
- downloading of data files and study descriptions on users' computer.

Before your first use of Nesstar WebView, we suggest reading the document [Nesstar Guide](#), where you can familiarize yourself with the also the instructions on how to search our catalog.

Warning:

- to analyse and download data files you need to [register at ADP](#).
- Due to objective reasons, the Nesstar WebView does not include all of the studies, deposited in the [Catalog ADP](#).
- For studies in the Catalog ADP different level of descriptions may apply:
 - 1 - full study description,
 - 2 - full study description and codebook with names of variables from the data file,
 - 3 - full study description with names of variables with full question text.

Support: arhiv.podatkov@fdv.uni-lj.si

What do you find on website?

- ✓ Study description
- ✓ Data description
- ✓ Accompanying materials

What do you find on Nesstar?

- +
- ✓ Enables online analysis

<http://www.nesstar.com/help/4.0/webview/getting-started/getting-to-know-nesstar-webview.html>

Seznam raziskav po:

- Study ID
- Series**
- Study topics
- Depositors
- Year of Production
- Year of Publication
- Author
- International studies

Use data / / ADP Catalogue

List of studies from series SJM - Slovensko javno mnenje = Slovene Public Opinion Survey

Study ID	Study title, topic	Access
CESTE94	Slovene Public Opinion Survey 1994/3: Research on Highways in Slovenia. series: SJM , CESTE , topic: Not categorized, produced by: CJMMK	

SJM161

Slovenian Public Opinion 2016/1: Relation between Work and Family, Attitudes on family issues and needs of families, Attitudes on selected aspects of health and health care, Mirror of public opinion
series: **SJM**, topic: SOCIETY AND CULTURE, SOCIETY AND CULTURE - social behaviour and attitudes, SOCIETY AND CULTURE - social conditions and indicators, produced by: CJMMK

SJM15

Slovenian Public Opinion 2015: Work Orientation (ISSP 2015), Role of Government (ISSP 2016), Mirror of public opinion and National Security Survey
series: **SJM**, **ISSP**, topic: SOCIETY AND CULTURE, SOCIETY AND CULTURE - social behaviour and attitudes, SOCIETY AND CULTURE - social conditions and indicators, produced by: CJMMK

SJM14

Slovene Public Opinion 2014: European Social Survey
series: **SJM**, **ESS**, topic: SOCIETY AND CULTURE, SOCIETY AND CULTURE - social behaviour and attitudes, produced by: CJMMK

Slovene Public Opinion 2014: European Social Survey

[Study description](#)

[Data description](#)

[Accompanying Materials](#)

[Nesstar Browser](#)

Basic Study Information

ADP - IDNo: SJM14

Main author(s):

Kurdija, Slavko
Malnar, Brina

[Other co-workers »](#)

Data file producer:

CJM - *Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre (Ljubljana, Slovenia; 2014)*

Funding agency:

- (1): Agencija za raziskovalno dejavnost Republike Slovenije= Slovenian Research Agency
- (2): Agencija za raziskovalno dejavnost Republike Slovenije= Slovenian Research Agency, MRIC UL (PLMER)

Series:

- *SJM/Slovensko javno mnenje = Slovene Public Opinion Survey* [More »](#)
- *ESS/European Social Survey* [More »](#)

Vsebina raziskave

Keywords:

media reading, watching, listening, use of internet, trust in fellow-person, trust in political institutions, party voted for, election participation, political participation, political party preferences, membership in political parties, life satisfaction,

TERMS OF USE:

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[download data](#)
[study description](#)

Status of the study: 4 - Full Study description and XML DDI Codebook Data description with full questions text.

STUDY CLASSIFICATION:

9: highest range, comparative or continuous research, influential populations, with methodological excellence

How to CITE this study?

Kurdija, Slavko and Brina Malnar. Slovene Public Opinion 2014: European Social Survey [data file]. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede = Faculty of Social Sciences, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication

Methodology

Collection date:	7. October 2014 - 1. February 2015
Date of production:	2014
Country:	Slovenia
Geographic coverage:	Territory of the Republic of Slovenia
Unit of analysis:	individual
Universe:	All persons aged 15 and over, resident within private households, regardless of their nationality citizenship, language or legal status, residing in Slovenia.
Excluded:	Institutionalised inhabitants such as high-schoolers and students, living at dorms, persons serving in the army, persons being treated in hospitals and others who are not living at their registered addresses.
Data collected by:	Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre
Sampling procedure:	The sample is two-stage stratified random sample from Central Register of Population, where every population unit has equal probability of selection. First stage PSU selection is made by probability proportional to size of CEA (Clusters of Enumeration Areas). CEA are stratified according to 12 regions*6 type of settlement. At second stage systematic random selection inside CEA brings fixed numbers of persons with name and address.
Weighting:	No.

Access restrictions

Data and materials are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The users should use the materials only for the purposes specified in Registration form, to act at all times so as to preserve the confidentiality of individuals and institutions recorded in the materials.

Contact: Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov = Social Science Data Archives

The users should acknowledge in any publication both the original depositors and the Archive.

Users are requested to deposit with the Archive two copies of any published work or report based wholly or in part on such materials and to notify the Archive of any errors discovered in the materials.

Slovenian Public Opinion 2015: Work Orientation (ISSP 2015), Role of Government (ISSP 2016), Mirror of public opinion and National Security Survey

[Study description](#)

[Data description](#)

[Accompanying Materials](#)

[Nesstar Browser](#)

Materials of the Study

1. Hafner Fink, Mitja (2015). [SJM15 - Slovensko javno mnenje 2015: Pokazni vprašalnik \[Questionnaire\]](#).

Study Results Materials

1. Hafner Fink, Mitja (2015). [SJM15 - Slovensko javno mnenje 2015: Pregled rezultatov](#).
2. Blejec, Marjan (1969-1970). [POROČILA iz raziskave Slovensko javno mnenje 69: Načrti in analiza vzorcev za ankete "Slovensko javno mnenje" SJM68, SJM69 in SJM70](#).

Related Publications

1. Švara, Sergio (2016). [Vsebine anket SJM 1968 - 2016](#).
2. Toš, Niko (1997). [Vrednote v prehodu I. Slovensko javno mnenje 1968-1990](#).
3. Toš, Niko (1999). [Vrednote v prehodu II. Slovensko javno mnenje 1990-1998](#).
4. Toš, Niko (2004). [Vrednote v prehodu III. Slovensko javno mnenje 1999-2004](#).
5. Toš, Niko (2009). [Vrednote v prehodu IV. : slovensko javno mnenje 2004-2008](#).
6. Toš, Niko (2012). [Vrednote v prehodu V. : Slovenija v evropskih primerjavah : evropska družboslovna raziskava 2002-2010](#).
7. Toš, Niko (2012). [Vrednote v prehodu VI. : Slovenija v mednarodnih primerjavah 1992-2011 : \[evropska, svetovna raziskava vrednot 1992-2011\]](#).
8. Toš, Niko (2013). [Vrednote v prehodu VII. : Slovenija v mednarodnih in medčasnih primerjavah : SJM - ISSP 1991-2012](#).
9. Toš, Niko (2014). [Vrednote v prehodu VIII. : Slovenija v srednje in vzhodnoevropskih primerjavah : \[1991-2011\]](#).
10. Toš, Niko (2014). [Vrednote v prehodu IX. : Iz zakladnice socioloških raziskav: Migracije Slovencev in socialna struktura jugoslovanske družbe : \[1973 - 1987\]](#).
11. Toš, Niko (2016). [Vrednote v prehodu X. : Slovensko javno mnenje \[2010 - 2016\]](#).
12. Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre (2013). [E-dokumenti CJM](#).
13. Tóka, Gábor (2000). [Inventory of political attitude and behaviour surveys in East Central Europe and the former Soviet Union 1989-1997](#).

Dataset: [SJM15]³ Slovenian Public Opinion 2015 : Work Orienta

Work Orientation (ISSP 2015), Role of Government (ISSP 2016), Mirror of publi

Download

Please select a data format from the drop-down box.
If you wish to download a subset of the data, click on the 'Subset' button.
Click on 'Download' to start downloading.
Please note that you may be asked for a password.

SPSS Portable ▼

DOWNLOAD

SUBSET

Include computed variables

Download the documentation

Please select a download format from the drop-down box.
Click on 'Download' to start downloading.

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Please select a data format from the drop-down box.
If you wish to download a subset of the data, click on the 'Subset' button.
Click on 'Download' to start downloading.
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SUBSET

Include computed variables

Download the documentation

Please select a download format from the drop-down box.
Click on 'Download' to start downloading.

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nesstar

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[study description](#)

Status of the study: 4 - Full Study description and XML DDI
Codebook Data description with full questions text.

STUDY CLASSIFICATION:

9: highest range, comparative or continuous research,
influential populations, with methodological excellence

How to CITE this study?

Hafner Fink, Mitja and Marjan Malešič. Slovenian Public Opinion 2015: Work Orientation (ISSP 2015), Role of Government (ISSP 2016), Mirror of public opinion and National Security Survey [data file]. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre [production], 2015. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov = Social Science Data Archives [distribution], 2016. ADP - IDNo: SJM15.

Citation style APA6:

Hafner - Fink, M. in Malešič, M.
(2016). **Slovenian Public Opinion 2015: Work Orientation (ISSP 2015), Role of Government (ISSP 2016), Mirror of public opinion and National Security Survey** [Data file]. Ljubljana: University of Ljubljana, Social Science Data Archives. ADP - IDNo: SJM15. Available at <http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/sjm15/>.

ELEMENTS OF DATA CITATION

- **Author:** Name(s) of each individual or organizational entity responsible for the creation of the dataset.
- **Date of Publication:** Year the dataset was published or disseminated.
- **Title:** Complete title of the dataset, including the edition or version number, if applicable.
- **Publisher and/or Distributor:** Organizational entity that makes the dataset available by archiving, producing, publishing, and/or distributing the dataset.
- **Electronic Location or Identifier:** Web address or unique, persistent, global identifier used to locate the dataset (such as a DOI). Append the date retrieved if the title and locator are not specific to the exact instance of the data you used.

[Source: IASSIST, 2012: Quick guide to data citation](#)

Registration form

Use data / / How to Get Data? / / 4. Register

4. REGISTER

Publication date: 28. 09. 2017 Revision date: 11. 10. 2017

Večina podatkov iz kataloga ADP je uporabnikom dostopna šele po registraciji. Za dostop do podatkov je potrebno izpolniti obrazec, v katerem se uporabnik identificira, opredeli uporabo gradiva in izrazi strinjanje s Splošnimi določili in pogoji uporabe. Za dostop do občutljivejših podatkov mora uporabnik izpolniti tudi Vlogo za dostop do gradiva na zahtevo.

Please fill-in the form with the needed information. The fields that are marked with * are mandatory. Based on your request, we will provide you with a username and password that will be send to you on your e-mail address. Further information is available in the »Help with completing the registration form«

Fields marked with * are mandatory. Please fill them out.

First name*: ⓘ

Last name*: ⓘ

Organization: ⓘ

Address*: ⓘ

Email address*: ⓘ

Email address confirmation*: ⓘ

User category*: ⓘ

Researcher code: ⓘ

Purpose of use*: ⓘ

Mark down whether the results of your work will be used for commercial or non-commercial purposes.

Results of working with the data are intended for the following use*: ⓘ

Help with completing the registration form

[Forgotten password](#)

[Access to data](#)

VLOGA ZA DOSTOP DO GRADIV NA ZAHTEVO

Za dostop pod posebnimi pogoji je potrebno izpolniti vlogo. Več o tem v rubriki »Dostop pod posebnimi pogoji«.

Vloga za dostop

For a user name instead of "@" enter "AT"

Password is valid till 30.9.

... at the end of registration form

Select how you are going to use the material. You can choose between *online data analysis* or *downloading data*. In the latter case you have to analyse data in a suitable statistical program.

Purpose of use of the materials. I will use the materials*:

-- Select --
-- Select --
1) data will be analysed online
2) data will be downloaded on a local computer

Materials on demand:

Ne
 Da

Message for ADP:

I'm not a robot

reCAPTCHA
[Privacy - Terms](#)

Content preview

You can choose between analyzing data on web (for less skilled users) or transferring to your computer where you can analyze data in statistical programs. Depending on the access restrictions of each research, user category, purpose of use and method of analysis, various user profiles are created.

International data

Basic registration required

[ZACAT](#), [DBK](#), [DATORIUM](#)

cessda eric

Variable and question bank

CESSDA ERIC

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

The vision of CESSDA is to provide **full scale sustainable research infrastructures** that enables the research community to conduct high-quality research which in turn leads to effective solutions to the major challenges facing society today.

CESSDA's main tasks

- Coordinate the network of European data service providers
- Promote the results of social sciences
- **Facilitate researcher access to important resources of relevance to the European social science research agenda regardless of the location of either researcher or data**
- Include further data sources
- Provide training
- Promote wider participation in CESSDA
- Develop and coordinate standards, protocols and professional best practices

@CESSDA countries, 2017

Rotating modules for ESS Round 8 announced

The ESS ERIC Scientific Advisory Board has selected the two successful modules for ESS Round 8. More...

29 Countries

The 3rd International ESS Conference • 13-15th July 2016 • Lausanne, Switzerland [MORE >>](#)

Methodological Research

The European Social Survey runs a programme of research to support and enhance the methodology that underpins the high standards it pursues in every aspect of survey design, data collection and archiving.

Data and Documentation

Data and documentation can be accessed by round (year), by theme or by country. Data are available for download and online analysis.

ESS Resources

The ESS provides a series of outreach resources designed to increase the use of its data, including ESS Bibliography, Findings, Training Courses and eLearning resources.

About ESS

About ESS
Contact Information
Project Specification
Structure and Governance
Funding
News
Participating Countries
National Pages
User Statistics
Conference 2016

Methodology

ESS Methods Overview
Sampling
Translation
Questionnaire
Pre-Testing and Piloting
Improving Question Quality
Response and Non-Response
Mixed Mode Data Collection
Measuring National C
Attitudinal Indicators

Data and Documentation

Data and Documentation by Year
Data and Documentation by Country
Data and Documentation by Theme
Online Analysis
ESS Data Alerts
Conditions of Use
Fieldwork Summary and Deviations
Cumulative Data (Wizard)

Resources

ESS Bibliography
ESS EduNet (eLearning)
ESS Findings
ESS Training Courses
ESS on Wellbeing

About ESS Methodology Data and Documentation Resources

search

Home » Bibliography » Bibliography

ESS Bibliography

The ESS Bibliography contains information about public national European Social Survey. This includes analysis methodology research and descriptions and documents

family

SEARCH

ADVANCED SEARCH | SEARCH TIPS

The complete bibliography referenced in compliance with the Harvard System

<< first < prev 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 next > last >>

Search results: 158 hits (click on column headers to sort)

Title	Author(s)	Year	Type	Published in/by
Educational inequality as an example of unsustainable use of human resources	Beilmann, Mai Roots, Ave Sammul, Marek	2015	Conference paper/poster	
Neo-Nationalism in Western Europe	Eger, Maureen A. Valdez, Sarah	2015	Journal article	European Sociological Review
Prevention of social exclusion of elderly people and support for active and dignified ageing	Õun, Kandela Rähn, Anne	2014	Book chapter	Sustainable Welfare in a Regional Context
Who have the right to live as a family in Estonia?	Kurs, Eveliis Ainsaar, Mare	2014	Newspaper/magazine article	Eesti Ekspress
Is there class society in Estonia? Who are the rich, who are the poor	Päärt, Villu	2014	Newspaper/magazine article	Õhtuleht
Patterns of Family Life Courses in Europe – between Standardisation and Diversity: A Cross-national Comparison of Family Trajectories and Life Course Norms in European Countries	Hofäcker, Dirk Chaloupková, J.	2014	Journal article	Comparative Population Studies
Modelling the relationships between work-to-family conflict, work and family stressors and well-being	Fedáková, Denisa Dobeš, Marek	2014	Journal article	Člověk a společnost - Individual and Society
Work-family conflict in Sweden and Germany: A study on the association with self-rated health and the role of gender attitudes and family policy	Tunlid, Sara	2014	Thesis, dissertation	
Does gender matter? Policies, norms and the gender gap in work-to-home and home-to-work conflict across Europe	Fahlén, Susanne	2014	Journal article	Community, Work and Family
Töö- ja pereelu tasakaalustamine Eesti infotehnoloogiaettevõtetes	Taba, Nele	2013	Thesis, dissertation	
Is Old Age Stigma?	Rapoliéné, Gražina	2013	Conference paper/poster	
Comparison of Perception Safety in Relation to Selected Work Attributes in the Countries of the European Social Survey	Bozogáňová, Miroslava Tomková, Jana	2013	Conference paper/poster	
Chances and Challenges of demographic change	Blinkert, Baldo	2013	Book	LIT Verlag Münster
Capabilities and Childbearing Intentions in Europe: The association between reconciliation policies, economic uncertainties and women's fertility	Fahlén, Susanne	2013	Journal article	European Societies

DESCRIPTION

TABULATION

ANALYSIS

ESS

- ESS1-2002, ed.6.4
- ESS2-2004, ed.3.4
- ESS3-2006, ed.3.5
- ESS4-2008, ed.4.3
- ESS5-2010, ed.3.2
- ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

 Metadata

 Study Description

 Variable Description

- Country
- Weights
- Media and social trust
- Politics
- Subjective well-being, social exclusion, religion, national and ethnic identity
- Personal and social well-being
- Gender, Year of birth and Household grid
- Socio-demographics
- Human values
- Administrative variables
- Understanding of democracy
- User defined variables

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Abstract

The European Social Survey (ESS) is an academically-driven multi-country survey, which has been administered in over 30 countries to date. Its three aims are, firstly – to monitor and interpret changing public attitudes and values within Europe and to investigate how they interact with Europe's changing institutions, secondly - to advance and consolidate improved methods of cross-national survey measurement in Europe and beyond, and thirdly - to develop a series of European social indicators, including attitudinal indicators.

In the sixth round, the survey covers 29 countries and employs the most rigorous methodologies. It is funded via the European Commission's 7th Framework Programme, the European Science Foundation and national funding bodies in each country.

The survey involves strict random probability sampling, a minimum target response rate of 70% and rigorous translation protocols. The hour-long face-to-face interview includes questions on a variety of core topics repeated from previous rounds of the survey and also two modules developed for Round Six covering Europeans' Understandings and Evaluations of Democracy and Personal and Social Wellbeing (the latter is a partial repeat of a module from round 3).

Full Title

ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Alternative Title

ESS6-2012

Identification Number

ESS6e02.1

Bibliographic Citation

European Social Survey (2014). ESS Round 6 (2012/2013) Technical Report. London: Centre for Comparative Social Surveys, City University London

Martin: Centre for Comparative Social Surveys (CCSS), City University London, UK. Geert Loosveldt, Jaak Billiet and Hideko Matsuo: Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium. Bjørn Henrichsen, Knut Kalgraff Skjåk, and Kirstine Kolsrud: Norwegian Social Science Data Services (NSD), Norway. Angelika Scheuer, Sabine Häder, Achim Koch, Matthias Ganninger, Verena Halbherr, Brita Dorer and Stefan Zins: GESIS, Germany. Willem Saris, Wiebke Weber, Diana Zavala Rojas and Bruno Arpino: Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain. Ineke Stoop, Joost Kappelhof and Henk Fernee: The Netherlands Institute for Social Research (SCP), Netherlands. Brina Malnar: University of Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Let's start with a simple exercise comparing **life satisfaction measures** of two groups – **the unemployed people looking for work** versus **people in paid work**. Calculate the **means** for the two groups across Europe.

Variable mnactic: Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded

LITERAL QUESTION

F17c2. POST CODE: I

Values	Categories	Code	Frequency	% of all	% of valid
	Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded				
1	Paid work	1	25,760	47.1	47.6
2	Education	2	4,704	8.6	8.7
3	Unemployed, looking for job	3	2,978	5.4	5.5
4	Unemployed, not looking for job	4	1,155	2.1	2.1
5	Permanently sick or disabled	5	1,291	2.4	2.4
6	Retired	6	12,819	23.4	23.7
7	Community or military service	7	90	0.2	0.2
8	Housework, looking after children, others	8	4,796	8.8	8.9
9	Other	9	520	1.0	1.0
66	Not applicable				
77	Refusal	77	39	0.1	-
88	Don't know	88	105	0.2	-
99	No answer	99	416	0.8	-
	Total		54,673	100.0	100.0

SUMMARY STATISTICS

This variable is numerical

Socio-demographics

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

- Doing last / days: no answer
- Interviewer code, one/more than one doing last 7 days
- Main activity last 7 days
- Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post code
- Interviewer code, respondent in p
- Control paid work last 7 days
- Ever had a paid job
- Year last in paid job
- Employment relation
- Number of employees respondent
- Employment contract unlimited or limited duration
- Establishment size

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

Choose 'Add to column' to place the variable here.

To populate this table you need to select a variable from the browse list, click on it and then add it to row, column or layers, or use it as a measure variable.

Politics

- Placement on left right scale
- How satisfied with life as a whole
- How satisfied with present state
- How satisfied with the national g
- How satisfied with the way demo
- State of education in country now
- State of health services in countr
- Government should reduce differences in income levels
- Gays and lesbians free to live life as they wish

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

B20. All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?

	Median	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation	Sum	Count
Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded							
Paid work	7.5	7.0	0.0	10.0	2.2	179,423.0	25,653
Education	8.0	7.7	0.0	10.0	1.9	35,885.0	4,676
Unemployed, looking for job	5.6	5.4	0.0	10.0	2.7	16,028.0	2,956
Unemployed, not looking for job	5.7	5.6	0.0				9
Permanently sick or disabled	5.6	5.5	0.0				8
Retired	7.0	6.5	0.0				5
Community or military service	7.6	6.9	0.0				0
Housework, looking after children, others	7.2	6.6	0.0				7
Other	7.6	7.0	0.0				7
Total	7.30	6.76	0.00				1

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Main activity, la...dents. Post coded	Median	Average
All	7.5	7.0
✓ Categories	8.0	7.7
Change selection...	5.6	5.4
Move to column	5.7	5.6
Use as Filter	5.6	5.5
Remove from table	7.0	6.5
Insert calculation	7.6	6.9
Permanently sick or disabled		
Retired		
Community or military service		

Change selection ✕

Search for categories OK

- All
- Paid work
- Education
- Unemployed, looking for job
- Unemployed, not looking for job
- Permanently sick or disabled
- Retired
- Community or military service
- Housework, looking after children, others
- Other

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Satisfaction with life vs. employment

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Next, let's confirm the [correlation](#) between providing help and life satisfaction. Is it [significant](#)? Make sure you check variables response codes to be sure – for ex. do high numbers mean satisfaction or do they mean low satisfaction? Use the variables '(B20) How satisfied with life as a whole' and '(D37) Provide help and support to people you are close to'.

LITERAL QUESTION

B20. All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?
extremely satisfied.

Values	Categories
0	Extremely dissatisfied
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
6	6
7	7
8	8
9	9
10	Extremely satisfied
77	Refusal
88	Don't know
99	No answer

D37. And to what extent do you provide help and support to

Values	Categories
0	Not at all
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
6	Completely
7	Refusal

DESCRIPTION	TABULATION	ANALYSIS
CORRELATION	REGRESSION	

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Listwise Correlation analysis: [\[Change to pairwise\]](#)

Variables:
No variables added

Choose variables from the browse list.

Politics

- Placement on left-right scale
- How satisfied with life as a whole Add to correlation.
- How satisfied with present state
- How satisfied with the national government
- How satisfied with the way democracy works in country

Personal and social well-being

- Receive help and support from people you are close to
- Provide help and support to people you are close to Add to correlation.
- Your place in society
- Physically active for 20 minutes or longer last 7 days

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Listwise Correlation analysis: [\[Change to pairwise\]](#)

Variables:

How satisfied with life as a whole [\[Remove\]](#)
 Receive help and support from people you are close to [\[Remove\]](#)

	How satisfied with life as a whole	
Receive help and support from people you are close to	0.272 **	** p < 0.01 * p < 0.05

B25. Still using this card, please say what you think overall about the state of health services in [country] nowadays?

Values	Categories
0	Extremely bad
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
6	6
7	7
8	8
9	9
10	Extremely good
77	Refusal
88	Don't know
99	No answer

Variables:

How satisfied with life as a whole [\[Remove\]](#)
 State of health services in country nowadays [\[Remove\]](#)

	How satisfied with life as a whole	
State of health services in country nowadays	0.373 **	** p < 0.01 * p < 0.05

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Country: Categories Measure: State of health s...nowadays, average

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Use help!!

Front Page

GETTING STARTED

- Nesstar Webview
- Using Webview
- Exploring Data
- Creating Tables
- Manipulate Tables
- Analysis
- Graphics

SEARCH

- Simple Search
- Advanced Search
- Search Results

METADATA

- Description
- Metadata

TOOLS

- Insert Calculation
- Subset by Cases
- Weighting
- Compute and Recode
- Recode
- Bookmarks

DOWNLOAD

- Download Data & Documentation
- Subset Data
- Save Output

Compute and Recode

The 'Compute' option provides pre-defined mathematical and statistical functions to convert values of existing variables into new variables.

Note: For the Σ icon to be visible, you must use the Configuration tool. refer to [webview help](#).

To use the 'Compute' option:

1. Select the compute icon Σ . If no data is available, the system has no data.

The system will retrieve any variables you have previously generated or have access to.

2. If there are no previously generated variables a 'Create' box will appear containing a list of calculation types and the 'Recode' option.

Compute

Create

Please select a type of calculation Σ

Please select a type of calculation

- Add
- Subtract
- Multiply
- Divide
- Percent
- Average
- Percent growth
- Recode

3. Using the 'Create' box select a predefined formula, or 'Recode' to begin to compute a new variable.
4. If user defined variables already exist these can be deleted from the 'Delete' menu.

Download

Please select a data format from the drop-down box. If you wish to download a subset of the data, click on the 'Subset' button. Click on 'Download' to start downloading. Please note that you may be asked for a password.

-- Select Data Format -- Σ DOWNLOAD SUBSET

Include computed variables

Include documentation

SPSS, STATA, SAS, R

Download the documentation

Please select a download format from the drop-down box. Click on 'Download' to start downloading.

In pdf format Σ DOWNLOAD

FINDING DATA

ADVANCED SEARCH

Advanced Search - Mozilla Firefox

zocat.gesis.org/webview/velocity?mode=searchview&searchtype=advanced&&

Advanced Search

Search criteria:

Variable contains health

Search for: datasets variables

Study Description

- Study Description
- Bibliographic Citation
- Title Statement
- Full Title
- Identification Number
- Responsibility Statement
- Authoring Entity
- Production Statement
- Producer
- Copyright
- Funding Agency/Sponsor
- Distributor Statement
- Data Distributor
- Abbreviation
- Depositor
- Study Scope
- Subject Information
- List of Keywords
- Topic Classification
- Abstract

SEARCH

ZA4768: EVS 2008: Lithuania
[ZA4768 Datafiles and Documentation download](#) (via data catalogue)

Variable v9: describe your state of health these days (Q4)

LITERAL QUESTION
Q4
<SHOW CARD 4>
All in all, how would you describe your state of health these days? Would you say it is

- 5 other missing
- 4 question not asked
- 3 nap
- 2 na
- 1 dk
- 1 very good
- 2 good
- 3 fair
- 4 poor
- 5 very poor

Example of international data - GESIS

DESCRIPTION

TABULATION

ANALYSIS

International Social Survey
Programme: Role of Government I-IV
(ISSP 1985-1990-1996-2006)

Metadata

Variable Description

Archive and ID variables

Substantial variables

Obey laws without
exception

Public protest meetings

Protest publications

Protest demonstrations

Occupation gov. office

Damage gov. buildings

National anti-government
strike

Revolutionaries: hold public
meetings

Revolutionaries: publish
books

Racist: hold public meetings

Racist: publish books

Known criminal: police tail

Known criminal: tap phone

Known criminal: open mail

Known criminal: police
detain

Worse type of justice error

Computer threat privacy

How much income tax rich

Government: redistribute
wealth

Government: control wages
by law

ZA4747: International Social Survey Programme: Role of Government I-IV (ISSP 1985-1990-1996-2006)

[ZA4747 Datafiles and Documentation download](#) (via data catalogue)

Variable V21: Known criminal: open mail

LITERAL QUESTION

ZA1490: Q.5A.III, ZA1950: Q.5III

Suppose the police get an anonymous tip that a man with a long criminal record is planning to break into a warehouse.

Do you think the police should be allowed without a court order to...

Open his mail

in ZA2900 (1996):

Variable not available in this module.

in ZA4700 (2006):

Variable not available in this module.

-9 NA, refused

-8 Cant choose, dont know

-3 Variable not available in this module

-1 Variable not available for this country in this module

1 Definitely allowed

2 Probably allowed

3 Probably not allowed

4 Definitely not allowed

Example of international data - GESIS

ZA4747: International Social Survey Programme: Role of Government I-IV (ISSP 1985-1990-1996-2006)

[ZA4747 Datafiles and Documentation download](#) (via data catalogue)

Country: Categories Measure: Known criminal: open mail, average

Politics

Religion

Work

Family

Society

Well-being

Europe

How well one's own system of government is functioning

Importance of politics

Individual responsibility versus state responsibility

Interest in politics

Joining in boycotts

Left or right political views

Less emphasis on money and material possessions would be good

Occupying buildings or factories

Participation in elections

Personal freedom more important than equality

Private ownership versus government ownership

Satisfaction with development of democracy in one's own country

Signing petitions

Society must be defended against all changes

Society must be gradually changed through reform

Atlas of European Values

Atlas

European Values

Home

European maps

World maps

Teaching materials

Videos

Old website

Percentage of people that agree that both freedom and equality are important. But if they were to choose, they would consider personal freedom more important.

Graph

Click on the country in the list below for results of the last 4 surveys

1981

1990

1999

2008

Countries

Albania	63
Armenia	57
Austria	56
Azerbaijan	46
Belarus	50

Data by country

Austria
Belgium
Bulgaria
Croatia
Cyprus
Czech Republic
Denmark
Estonia
Finland
France
Germany
Greece
Hungary
Iceland
Ireland
Italy
Latvia
Liechtenstein
Lithuania
Luxembourg
Macedonia
Malta
Montenegro
Netherlands
Norway
Poland
Portugal
Romania
Slovakia
Slovenia

that incorporate additional statistical measures as demography, labour market, etc.

Data are collected from national election authorities, national statistical agencies and other official sources.

Click on the labels to explore the data.

Slovenia

HEAD OF STATE: President Dr Borut Pahor

HEAD OF GOVERNMENT: Prime Minister Janez Janša

NATIONAL ASSEMBLY (*DRŽAVNI ZBOR*): 90 members

LAST ELECTION: Presidential, 11 November and 2 December 2012

NEXT ELECTION: Legislative, due in 2015

Parliamentary Elections

[OPEN ORIGINAL](#) [LAST UPDATED 1/18/13](#)

Presidential Elections

Election results 2012. Electoral

[OPEN ORIGINAL](#) [LAST UPDATED 1/18/13](#)

Candidate	
Round	Region
	SLOVENIA
	Kranj
	Postojna
	Ljubljana Center

Presidential Elections

Election results 2012. Electoral Districts

[OPEN ORIGINAL](#) [LAST UPDATED 1/18/13](#)

Candidate		PAHOR	TÜRK	ZVER	
Round	Region				
1	SLOVENIA	39.87	35.88	24.25	
	Kranj	37.43	33.95	28.62	
	Postojna	46.21	34.28	19.50	
	Ljubljana Center	35.34	41.79	22.88	
	Ljubljana Bezigrad	37.67	39.00	23.32	
	Celje	43.78	32.81	23.41	
	Novo Mesto	40.20	36.02	23.78	
	Maribor	41.79	36.17	22.03	
	Ptuj	38.03	32.23	29.74	
	Other	19.02	28.31	52.66	
	2	SLOVENIA	67.37	32.63	-
		Kranj	69.00	31.00	-
Postojna		70.03	29.97	-	
Ljubljana Center		58.85	41.15	-	
Ljubljana Bezigrad		62.94	37.06	-	
Celje		71.79	28.21	-	
Novo Mesto		69.18	30.82	-	
Maribor		66.75	33.25	-	
Ptuj		72.39	27.61	-	
Other		65.46	34.54	-	

46.21 34.28 19.50

35.34 41.79 22.88

Elections 1990–2015

Year	Parl	Pres	EP	Ref
1989				
1990				
1991				
1992	Q	Q		
1993				
1994				
1995				
1996	Q			
1997		Q		
1998				
1999				
2000	Q			
2001				
2002		Q		
2003				Q
2004	Q		Q	
2005				
2006				
2007		Q		
2008	Q			
2009			Q	
2010				
2011	Q			
2012		Q		
2013				
2014				

CIMES - Centralizing and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics

- information system providing an overview of European official microdata disseminated for research purposes
- structured metadata for national official statistics microdata
- 3 levels of metadata:
series, study and dataset
- 31 European countries, 248 series, 1570 studies, 1821 datasets documented

The screenshot displays the CIMES web application interface. The header includes the CIMES logo and the tagline 'Centralising and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics'. A user is logged in as 'Reader DwiB'. The main content area is divided into two sections:

- Series and studies for SLOVENIA:** A list of various statistical series, including 'Census', 'Central Population Register (CPR)', 'Community Innovation Survey (CIS)', 'European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC)', 'External Trade', 'Final accounts', 'Graduates in tertiary education', 'Gross Fixed Capital Formation', 'Household Budget Survey (HBS)', 'Industrial production', 'Labour Force Survey (LFS)', 'Personal Income Tax', 'Slovenian Business Register', 'Statistical Register of Employment', 'Student enrolment in tertiary education', 'Time Use Survey (TUS)', and 'Unemployed workers'. The 'Census' series is highlighted in blue.
- Study Details for 'Census - 2011':**
 - Original Title:** Popis - 2011
 - Original Alternative Title:** Registrski popis - 2011
 - English Alternative Title:** Register-based Census - 2011
 - Producer:** SORS.
 - Abstract:** The register-based census is one of the regular statistical surveys conducted by the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia and has the content basis in the Regulation (EC) No. 763/2008 of the European Parliament and the Council of 9 July 2008 on Population and Housing Censuses, Official Journal of the European Union L 218/14, 13 August, 2008. In accordance with Article 4 of the Regulation the methods of data collection are left to EU Member States. Slovenia's decision on the register-based census as a method of collecting and processing data was adopted with the Medium-Term Programme of Statistical Surveys 2008-2012 (Official Journal of the RS, No. 119/2007) and the Annual Programme of Statistical Surveys for 2011 (Official Journal of the RS, No. 93/2010). The method of data collection used in the register-based census where SORS links existing statistical and administrative data collections is also used in most of the statistical surveys. Acquisition and integration of data is allowed by Articles 32 and 33 of the National Statistics Act (Official Journal of the RS, No. 45/95 and 9/2001, consolidated text). All administrative sources from which we take over the data have the legal basis for the primary collection in the laws governing a particular source. The results of this integration and data processing are aggregated data and the identification of individuals is not possible. With the transition to the register-based census, Slovenia joins few European countries that have already implemented this way of collecting and processing data on population, households and dwellings (Denmark, Finland, Netherlands, Iceland) or will do so for the first time in 2011 (Austria, Belgium, Sweden, Norway). By doing this, Slovenia has not only reduced the administrative burden but also saved EUR 14 million.

MISSY - Microdata Information System for Official Statistics

- online service platform providing structured metadata for official statistics, including Eurostat microdata
- covering **Adult Education Survey, EU Labour Force Survey, EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions, Community Innovation Survey, Structure of Earnings Survey**
- 5 levels of metadata:
series, study, country study, dataset and variable levels
- distribution channel for „setup files“ – software program codes for import and basic processing of EU microdata

The screenshot shows the MISSY web interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Missy-Home', 'General Information', 'Find Metadata', and 'Work with myMetadata'. Below this is a search bar and a 'Variables in myMetadata Box' indicator. The main content area displays 'Series: CIS' with a dropdown menu for 'via Series' showing options like AES, CIS, EU-LFS, and EU-SILC. A table below the dropdown shows 'Select Study of CIS' with columns for year (2008, 2006) and count (4, 3). The 'Abstract' section provides a detailed description of the Community Innovation Survey (CIS). A sidebar on the right lists various metadata categories: Data Version, Keywords, Processing, Data Access, Data Service, Comparability, Notes, and References.

DFG

DwB

Mitglied der
Leibniz
Leibniz-Gemeinschaft

adp

When you do your own research

-> Time spend in managing your data at first half our your project will save time when writing paper.

„**Research data management** is about looking after your data. It concerns the development and implementation of practices, procedures, and policies to protect, validate, and describe data. Doing this ensures its quality, thereby facilitating potential reuse.“ (CESSDA ERIC, 2017)

[CESSDA User Guide RDM](#)

Research data lifecycle

"Practical guidance
for anyone working
with research data"

In [this book](#) there is
guidance on:

- how to plan data management and data sharing for your research
- how to document and describe content for data
- how to format and organise research data
- how to store and transfer data
- research ethics and privacy in data sharing and intellectual property rights
- data strategies for collaborative research
- how to publish and cite research data
- opportunities and limitations in using other people's research data, illustrated with real-life data reuse cases

Tools

This is **UKDS** selection of tools and templates that researchers may find useful for various data management tasks in social sciences research:

[Model consent form](#) that takes into account consent for data sharing and future data reuse

[Sample survey consent statement](#) that considers consent for data sharing and future data reuse

[Transcription template](#) of our preferred uniform style and layout for transcripts deposited with us

Example [transcription instructions](#) to help transcribers use a consistent style, layout and editing

[Transcription confidentiality agreement](#) to ensure that audio recordings and transcripts that may contain personal and confidential information about interviewees is handled correctly by a transcriber

[Data list template](#) to create an informative overview guide of a collection of interview transcripts or other qualitative data

[Data management costing tool](#) to help cost data management tasks in a research grant application

[Text anonymisation tool](#) to help you find disclosive information to remove or pseudonymise in qualitative textual data files.

UK Data Service

Still needed

Do you have your own research ID?

ORCID

Connecting Research
and Researchers

USE YOUR ORCID ID

Include your ORCID identifier on your Webpage, when you submit publications, apply for grants, and in any research workflow to ensure you get credit for your work.

[DDC - Data management planning check-list](#)

PREPARING RESEARCH DATA FOR OPEN ACCESS

Guide for data producers

Janez Štebe, Sonja Bežjak, Irena Vipavc Brvar

PRIPRAVA RAZISKOVALNIH PODATKOV ZA ODPRTI DOSTOP

Priručnik za raziskovalce

Janez Štebe, Sonja Bežjak, Irena Vipavc Brvar

Contact

Univerza v Ljubljani
Fakulteta za družbene vede
Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov
Kardeljeva ploščad 5
1000 Ljubljana

www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si

arhiv.podatkov@fdv.uni-lj.si

Arhiv.Druzboslovnih.Podatkov

@ArhivPodatkov

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seriss SYNERGIES FOR EUROPE'S
RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES
IN THE SOCIAL SCIENCES

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